

Extraction-Photometric Determination of Selenium with *o*-Mercapto Acetoacetanilide and Application to Mud Samples*

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Selenium forms an 1 : 2 complex with *o*-mercapto acetoacetanilide at pH 1. The complex has been quantitatively extracted into chloroform and the absorbance measured at 525 nm. Beer's law has been found to be obeyed for 90-700 ppm of selenium. Various foreign ions like Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Al^{3+} , In^{3+} , Te^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} , AsO_4^{3-} , Cl^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} and tartrate were tolerated in various amounts while Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , Fe^{2+} and Bi^{3+} were removed as their phosphate before extraction. CN^- , EDTA and citrate have been found to interfere. The method was employed for the analysis of selenium in mud samples. The relative standard deviation was found to be $\pm 2.49\%$ and the confidence interval was 198.69 ± 1.56 ppm selenium for 95% confidence interval for 7 determinations. The structure of the ligand and the composition of the complex have been discussed.

A number of thioligands viz., mercapto benzothiazole^{1,2}, thionaphthonic acid³, 1,4-diphenylthiosemicarbazide^{4,5}, naphthylbismuthiol⁶, thiosalicylamide⁷, *o*-hydroxythiobenzhydrazide⁸, acetothioacetanilide⁹, etc. have been recommended for spectrophotometric determination of selenium. Most of these, excepting 2,3-diaminonaphthalene¹⁰ and acetothioacetanilide suffer either from low accuracy or interference due to other ions, especially tellurium.

In the present investigation, *o*-mercapto acetoacetanilide, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ (Structure I), has been employed as a new sensitive and selective reagent for the determination of selenium(IV) in presence

of different interfering ions including tellurium, separated by extraction with chloroform. The accuracy of the method is comparable to that for 2,3-diaminonaphthalene and acetothioacetanilide while the selectivity is better than that of 2,3-diaminonaphthalene. The sensitivity is also very high. The preparation and properties of the ligand and of the complex have been studied.

Experimental

***o*-Mercapto acetoacetanilide :** The reagent was prepared by condensation of *o*-aminothiophenol with ethylacetoacetate in toluene on a hot oil bath (110-115°). The compound was separated on

cooling in freezing mixture. The oil was taken in petroleum ether and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

A stock solution of the reagent (0.05 M) was made in 60% aqueous ethanol.

Standard selenium(IV) solution : Pure elemental selenium (E. Merck) was dissolved in conc. nitric acid and the solution was neutralised with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The selenium content was determined as element using hydroxylamine hydrochloride¹¹. The solution was diluted so that the final selenium concentration was 2.0 mg per ml.

Diverse ions : Stock solutions were prepared from pure samples of nitrates, chlorides and sulphates of various metal ions or other convenient salts.

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Apparatus : Absorbance was measured in a Beckman Double Beam (Model 26) UV-Visible spectrophotometer using a pair of matched 1 cm quartz cuvettes. The pH values were taken with a Beckman Zeromatic pH meter. The IR spectrum was recorded on a Beckman Acculab-10 Infrared spectrophotometer.

Procedure for the determination of selenium :

A known amount (1.0-6.0 ml) of the standard solution containing 1.0-6.0 mg of selenium was taken and dilute phosphoric acid solution was added to adjust the pH at 0.9-1.1. The mixture was then heated to 60-70° on a hot water bath for about 30 min, 5 ml of the reagent solution added

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and shaken. Two extractions were performed using 5 ml chloroform each time, and the organic layer was kept for 4 hr for complete development of the purple-red colour. It was then dehydrated with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance was measured at 525 nm against reagent blank.

Procedure for the determination of selenium in mud samples :

The selenium mud sample was fused with 1 : 1 Na_2CO_3 : KNO_3 in a nickel crucible and extracted with water. The extract was filtered and the filtrate was treated with conc. HCl to give a solution of strength less than 6 M HCl. The solution was then heated below 100° to expel chlorine etc¹¹. Finally, selenium content was determined in the solution by the proposed method. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM IN MUD SAMPLES* ; SELENIUM CONTENT : 121 $\mu\text{g/g}$ mud

Mud taken g	Se present μg	Se found μg	Rel. error %
0.629	76.1	75.2	-1.2
1.316	159.2	158.4	-0.5
0.978	118.3	119.4	+0.9
1.581	191.3	191.9	+0.3

* This sample was collected from G.S.I., Calcutta.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curve and Beer's law : The absorbance values of several extracts containing a known amount of selenium (90-800 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were recorded in the wave length range of 400-600 nm. In all cases reagent blanks were used as reference, though the absorbance due to the reagent was very low. It was found that the selenium(IV) complex had a λ_{max} at 525 nm and showed negligible absorbance above 600 nm and below 400 nm. However, the reagent curve showed a peak at 390 nm and had negligible absorbance above 515 nm. Beer's law was found to be valid up to 700 ppm of selenium.

Extracting solvent and stability of the complex : Chloroform was found to be the most suitable solvent. The complex was recovered to the extent of about 96% in the first step. The maximum intensity of the extract was reached after 4 hr and this remained unchanged even after 3 days.

Effect of pH and reagent concentration : The absorbance values indicated that the extraction was maximum when the pH was between 0.9 and 1.0. Experiments using 1.0 to 8.0 ml of the reagent solution for each extraction showed that 20 mg of it was sufficient for the quantitative extraction of 0.5 to 5.0 mg of selenium(IV) present in aqueous medium.

Effect of diverse ions : The tolerance limits of different foreign ions in the determination of selenium were studied. It was found that Be^{2+} (200 fold), Mg^{2+} (225 fold), Mn^{2+} (250 fold), Zn^{2+} (200 fold), Cd^{2+} (250 fold), Cu^{2+} (100 fold), Ni^{2+} (125

fold), Co^{2+} (125 fold), Al^{3+} (200 fold), In^{3+} (225 fold), Te^{4+} (150 fold), Th^{4+} (200 fold), UO_2^{2+} (100 fold), MoO_4^{2-} (200 fold), WO_4^{2-} (200 fold), AsO_4^{3-} (200 fold), PO_4^{3-} (2000 fold), Cl^- (1000 fold), NO_3^- (2000 fold), tartrate (500 fold) caused no interference with the determination. Metals like Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} were removed as their phosphates. CN^- , EDTA and citrate ions were found to interfere.

The determination was also possible in presence of more than one foreign ion. Thus, the method was actually tested for selenium determination in presence of the following mixtures of foreign ions, e.g. (a) Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} (100 fold each); (b) Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} (50 fold each); (c) Te^{4+} , As^{3+} (100 fold each) and (d) PO_4^{3-} , Cl^- , NO_3^- (1000 fold each).

Sensitivity of the method : The optimum concentration¹² range was 200-650 ppm of selenium in chloroform. Sandell sensitivity¹³ was 1.0 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Molar absorptivity and relative standard deviation were found to be $84.56 \pm 1.4\%$ $\text{l.mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 525 nm and $\pm 2.49\%$, respectively. The confidence interval was 198.69 ± 1.56 ppm for 95% confidence limit for 7 determinations.

The selenium mud sample containing 121 μg selenium per gram mud was analysed by the recommended procedure and the results are presented in Table 1.

Studies on the ligand : *o*-Mercapto acetoacetanilide possesses the advantage of high solubility in various organic solvents viz, alcohol, acetone, chloroform, isobutyl methyl ketone, benzene, ether. The compound is yellowish orange with m.p. at 142° . The elemental analysis showed N, 6.81; C, 57.29; H, 5.37; S, 15.40%. (Calcd. N, 6.69; C, 57.41; H, 5.26; S, 15.31%).

The infrared absorption spectrum of the ligand was analysed¹⁴ using KBr matrix. The bands at 1625 and 3305 cm^{-1} were respectively specific for (CO) and (NH) stretching. It is difficult to assign (SH) grouping¹⁴ and the weak absorption band at 2540 cm^{-1} was assigned for it¹⁵.

The nature of the complex : A small amount of the solid complex was isolated under conditions similar to that of the extraction, but the mixture was allowed to stand on a steam bath for about 1 hr. The precipitate was filtered through a sintered glass crucible, washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The compound crystallised from ethanol was purple-red (decomposition temperature, 112°).

The results of elemental analysis showed N, 5.36; S, 12.48; Se, 15.36%. (Calcd. N, 5.48; S, 12.52; Se, 15.45%). This indicated the ratio of selenium to the ligand in the complex as 1 : 2. The composition of the complex in solution was further verified by the conventional slope-ratio method. In this method selenium : ligand ratio was observed as 1 : 2 with the formation constant 8.60×10^4 at

22°. The probable composition of the complex is $\text{SeO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{NO}_2\text{S})_2$. A similar oxygenated complex of selenium has been reported earlier⁹ and the present complex is likely to be square-pyramidal¹⁵.

The infrared spectra of the complex was studied in the solid phase using KBr matrix. The result indicated the presence of (CO) band at 1610 cm^{-1} and (NH) stretching band at 3300 cm^{-1} . The presence of the weak band at 2520 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of free (SH) grouping as was found in the ligand. That the sulphur end of the ligand remains uncoordinated to metal can also be found in some other thio-ligands¹⁶. The present ligand thus behaves as a bidentate chelating agent.

References

1. A. N. POLUKAROV and M. MAKHMOTOV, *Acad. Nauk. Kaz.*, 1969, **9**, 85; *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, **73**, 83578a.
2. E. PAMANANSKAS and A. SULIUNIENE, *Chem. Chem. Technol.*, 1969, **10**, 25.
3. YU. A. ZOLOTOV and A. A. ALEKSEVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1971, **26**, 131.
4. G. F. PINAEV, I. P. NARKEVICH, S. A. LANGRCHAN, I. K. KALMONOVICH and I. K. OSHCH, *Prikl. Khim.*, 1972, **5**, 68; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **79**, 111874a.
5. V. S. FINAFETOVA and V. I. MURASHOVA, *Deposited Doc.*, 1977, VINITI 3481-77, p. 18; *Chem. Abs.*, 1979, **90**, 161617e.
6. A. I. BUSEV and L. N. SIMONOVA, *Geokhim. Anal. Metody Izuch. Veshchestv. Saltara Osad. Porod. Rud.*, 1974, **2**, 86; *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **87**, 77833c.
7. S. C. SHOME, M. MAJUMDAR and M. P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 256.
8. P. K. GANGOPADHYAY and S. C. SHOME, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1134.
9. T. PAL and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 791.
10. I. I. NAZARENKO, A. M. KISLOV and I. V. KISLOVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1970, **25**, 1135.
11. K. KODAMA, "Methods of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1963, p. 22, 222.
12. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Trace Metals", 3rd Edn., Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 83, 97.
13. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1956, p. 289.
14. G. T. BEHNKE and K. NAKAMOTO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 433.
15. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", revised 3rd Edn., Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1976, p. 422.
16. R. L. DUTTA and A. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 429.